

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KONAN****FIRST NAME: KOUAME JEAN****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA**

Formatted: Font: 10 pt

Formatted: Font: 10 pt

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The Author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago footnote (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The Author did use Zotero to insert references

The Author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10 pro)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **How does Zotero help with citing sources in a document?**

- By providing suggestions for citations.
- By automatically generating citations in various styles.**
- By sending reminder emails to include citations
- By offering a template to write citations by hand

Formatted: Font: 12 pt

Commented [KG1]: Ensure that all multiple-choice options have either a terminal punctuation or not. Be uniform. In any case, a comma does not end a sentence. Use either a period/full stop or a question mark. Review all options in this paper.

Formatted: Font: 12 pt

Formatted: Font: 12 pt

Formatted: Font: 12 pt

Formatted: Font: 12 pt

2. **What is the primary goal of qualitative research?**

- To quantify and measure variables
- To explore and understand complex phenomena.**

Moved (insertion) [1]

Formatted: Font: 12 pt

¹ [Laurent Cleenewerck, *Zotero Training – Part 1* \(Vimeo, 2016\).](#)

Deleted: Euclid. "Student Orientation-Print and Keep on Hand." Euclid University, 2018. *Zotero Training - EUCLID University ACA-401 and ACA-401D*, 2021.

² [Sampson, James P. Jr. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second ed. \(Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017\). \[insert page no. here.\]\(#\)](#)

Formatted: Font: Italic

Formatted: RP References, Justified

- To establish cause-and-effect relationships
- To generalize findings to a larger population

3. What is the primary purpose of a literature review in a quantitative research paper?

- To present the researcher's opinions.
- To provide background information and justify the research.³
- To summarize the research findings.
- To criticize the work of other researchers.

Deleted:

Formatted: Superscript

Formatted: Font: 12 pt

Formatted: Font: 12 pt

4. Which one is true regarding the Learning Management System (LMS) at EUCLID ?

- The primary purpose of the LMS at EUCLID is to facilitate online learning by providing a centralized platform for course materials, communication, and assessments
- The feature that allows students to access course materials, submit assignments, and engage in discussions is the "Course Dashboard" on the EUCLID LMS.
- In the "Resources" section of the EUCLID LMS, students can typically find lecture notes, supplementary readings, multimedia content, and other educational materials related to their courses.

Deleted: are

Formatted: Font: 12 pt

Commented [KG2]: Review all the options under this section and ensure only one is the correct answer.

Formatted: Font: 12 pt

Formatted: Font: 12 pt

Formatted: Font: 12 pt, Not Superscript/ Subscript

Formatted: Font: 12 pt

Formatted: EUCLID Wrong Answer

³ Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1. 4th ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

Formatted: Bibliography

The EUCLID LMS supports collaborative learning through features such as discussion forums, group assignments, and collaborative document editing tools that allow students to work together on projects.

The "Gradebook" feature in the EUCLID LMS do not allows both students and instructors to track and monitor individual and overall class performance, displaying grades for assignments, quizzes, and exams

Formatted: Font: 12 pt

5. What is a serious academic offense that students sometimes unintentionally commit when submitting papers?

Deleted:

Using a thesaurus excessively.

Including personal opinions.

Using direct quotes sparingly.

Paraphrasing without proper citation.⁵

Formatted: Font: 12 pt

6. What is the primary purpose of including references in an academic research paper?

Deleted:

To showcase the author's knowledge.

To provide evidence for the claims made in the paper.

Commented [KG3]: This should have a footnote!

Formatted: Font: 12 pt

To increase the word count of the paper.

To confuse the readers.

Deleted: ,

Deleted: Laurent

Deleted: .

Deleted: .

Deleted: 4th

Formatted: Font: Italic

Deleted: EUCLID

Formatted: Highlight

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), indicate the page number here.

7. When citing a journal article in the reference list, how should the title of the article be formatted according to the WHO style guide?

- Upper Case
- Title Case
- Sentence case
- Camel Case
- Italics.⁷

Deleted:

Deleted: UPPER CASE

8. Which of the following elements should be included in a Turabian-style bibliography entry for a book?

- Author's name, title of the book, publication date.
- Author's name, title of the book, page numbers.
- Author's name, title of the book, publisher, and publication date.⁸
- Author's name, title of the book, and city of publication.

Deleted:

Formatted: Font: 12 pt

Formatted: Font: 12 pt

9. When citing a book in the bibliography, what information should be included ?

- Book title, page number, publication date, author's name.
- Publisher, page number, author's name, book title.
- ISBN, author's name, book title, publication date

⁷ World Health Organization, *WHO Editorial Style Manual* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 1993), 52.

⁸ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph Bizup, Williams Fitzgerald, and University of Chicago Press Staff. Ninth ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018). indicate page number here.

Deleted: Kate L.

Deleted: 9th

Deleted: |

Formatted: Highlight

Author's name, book title, publication date, publisher.²

Formatted: Font: 12 pt

10. In Turabian style, how should in-text citations be formatted for a direct quote?

Deleted:

[Author's name, page number]

(Author's name, page number).⁶

Commented [KG4]: Change this to 10

Author's name, page number

Deleted:

Author's name (page number)

Formatted: Font: 12 pt

Formatted: Font: 12 pt

² Turabian, *Idem*.

Deleted: Kate L.

⁶ [Kate L. Turabian](#), *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, [insert page number here](#).

Deleted: Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph Bizup, Williams Fitzgerald, and University of Chicago Press Staff. 9th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Formatted: Highlight

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 4th ed. Bangui: EUCLID University, 2021.

Formatted: RP References, Justified

[Cleenewerck, Laurent. *Zotero Training – Part I*. Vimeo, 2016.](#)

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph Bizup, Williams Fitzgerald, and University of Chicago Press Staff. 9th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Deleted: Euclid. "Student Orientation-Print and Keep on Hand." Euclid University, 2018. *Zotero Training - EUCLID University ACA-401 and ACA-401D*, 2021. Accessed November 2, 2018, <https://vimeo.com/231577694>.

Sampson, James P, Jr. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second ed. Tallahassee: Florida State University, [2017](#).

Deleted: 2017.

World Health Organization. *WHO Editorial Style Manual*. Geneva: World Health Organization Press, 1993.

Formatted: RP References, Justified

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.